

HUTSUL FOLK COSTUMES IN THE COLLECTION OF THE SEWERYN UDZIELA ETHNOGRAFIC MUSEUM IN KRAKOW: THE HISTORY OF THE CREATION (EMBROIDERY, LACE MAKING, KNITTING)

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Olena KOZAKEVYCH

candidate of arts (Ph.D)

researcher, Folk Art Department,

Ethnology Institute of the National Academy of Sciences, Lviv, Ukraine;

Seweryn Udziela Ethnographic Museum in Krakow,

E-mail: kozakevych.olena@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-8742-4337

Summary. The Hutsul region is one of the most researched historical and ethnographic areas of Ukraine and the Carpathian region. In the research on the Hutsul folk costume in the collection of the Seweryn Udziela Ethnographic Museum in Krakow, or any other ethnic groups, it is important to take into consideration several important factors. The plans for the establishment of the Ethnographic Museum began in 1902 and were related to the exhibition on folk art from the collection of Seweryn Udziela, organized by the Polish Applied Arts Society. The National Museum in 1904 created an ethnographic department and a permanent ethnographic exposition in the Cloth Hall was opened. But the Ethnographic Museum was founded only in 1911 as an independent institution, thanks to Seweryn Udziela (1857–1937) – one of founders, first and only director. The following year after the death of the director museum was named in his honor.

The present collection of the Hutsul folk costumes stored at the Seweryn Udziela Ethnographic Museum of Kraków has been developed in several stages and is related to the history of two museums: the Museum of Technology and Industry (closed in 1950) and the National Museum in Krakow, where most of the MTI collections were transferred after its liquidation. These collected exhibits were transferred as a deposit from the National Museum to the MEK in 1939 and entered into the MEK Inventory Book in 1989. The origin of the artefacts is evidenced by the metrics on the objects, which to some extent emphasize the historical value of the collections and provide some data on the approximate age of the objects. The main part of the collection dates from the end of the 19th and the first half of the 20th centuries (until the outbreak of World War II). The Hutsul collection was assembled thanks to private donors.

During the query, objects from the «Hutsulshchyna» boxes and cabinets were selected, and marked in the inventory cards as «Hutsul», «Hutsul region» or «Ruthenians» are in fact of a different origin. The MEK collection consists of traditional clothing and accessories that complemented and added an air of uniqueness to the folk costume of the Hutsul region. This collection includes women's and men's garments and a few children's items: shirts, headgear, footwear, leather and woven belts, aprons, trousers, scarves, outerwear made of wool and leather. Detailed research on a topic requires a separate article, or even a monograph, whereas the aim of this text is to focus attention on the issues of scientific study of the collections of the Hutsul costumes at the MEK, their attribution and the artistic features of a number of exhibits. It is important to establish and corroborate the origin of the object, its terminology (local name), together with manufacturing techniques and patterns.

Hutsul folk art became an ethnic rotor promoting the Hutsul region far beyond its borders. This popularization resulted in an increased interest in collecting Hutsul artefacts and researching the material and spiritual culture of the Eastern Carpathian highlanders. To some extent, this is the reason why there are numerous and valuable collections in museums in other countries, including in Poland. One of such museums is the Seweryn Udziela Ethnographic Museum in Krakow, which has unique historical artefacts of the Hutsul folk costumes and textiles, which come mainly from the end of the

19th century and first three decades of the 20th century. Original ornaments, colours and types of garments and accessories show a local variety of the Hutsul clothing. This can be a foundation for an artistic interpretation of the collection. Nevertheless, a number of objects require a more precise attribution, and the collection in general needs further elaboration – in the context of social, cultural, ethnographic and local factors – in order to define and identify the phenomenon of the traditional Hutsul folk costume.

Keywords: Seweryn Udziela Ethnographic Museum in Krakow, Hutsul region, collections, folk costume, embroidery, lace making, knitting, tradition, ornaments

Hutsul region is one of the most studied historical and ethnographic areas of the Carpathian region. For almost two centuries, mountain landscapes, Hutsul traditional culture and folk art have attracted attention and delight both scientists and amateur researchers. To some extent, it contributed to the mythologization of the Hutsul region, in which the clothing of the highlanders can also be considered¹.

Polish museums have many collections that demonstrate the multicultural diversity of works of fine and decorative art. It manifests itself to a certain extent through the historical and artistic value of the collections, origin and content, which gives grounds for talking about their uniqueness and the accuracy of the research perspective. In terms of geographic, ethnic and ethnographic diversity of these collections, quite numerous collections of Hutsul art should be distinguished. The creation of museum collections began in the last thirty years of the XIX centuries, when museum activity intensified and museums occupied an important place in the cultural and educational life of the society. Exhibitions showing the achievements of technological progress, art and cultural diversity of the world (London 1851; Paris 1855, 1878; Moscow 1867; Vienna 1873; Prague 1900) played an important role in these processes.

In research on the Hutsul folk costume and different ornaments (embroidery, lace work, in the collection Seweryn Udziela Ethnographic Museum in Krakow, as well as other ethnic groups, it is important to take into account several important issues. First, the chronological framework: the fact that the Hutsul costumes, for example from the mid-nineteenth century and the interwar period, differed in typology, ways of decorating, and washed fabrics, which is related to the historical and socio-cultural changes that took place at that time. It is also worth taking into account the territorial boundaries of the Hutsul region: neighborhood with other ethnic groups, the influence of the cultures of other countries, which was very strongly manifested in clothing. It is also important to understand the issue of multi-ethnicity, multiculturalism of the Hutsul region (Ukrainians, Ruthenians, Poles, Jews, Armenians, Romanians, Germans) and the socio-professional diversity of the population (peasants, burghers, aristocracy, craftsmen, traders, educational workers, etc.), which can be will also trace in local art and style features of the garment. Each of these issues is in part considered in this text or in the development process as separate studies.

At that time, works of Hutsul art were mostly concentrated in private collections, but later these collections became the basis of the collections of newly emerging museums and for a long time were the main source of supplementing them. According to archival documents, works of art were bought, donated, exchanged between collectors and museums, and exhibited in Galicia and abroad. In this way, the history of each collection was created, the main directions of museum activity were outlined, and people who played a leading role in these processes were identified. The collections from the Hutsul region were supplemented particularly intensively in the first decade of the XX century. It was caused by several factors: the development of tourism in these areas, fascination with Hutsul folk art, promotion of highlander culture outside the region and, to some extent, the mythologization of the Hutsul region.

¹ О. Козакевич, *В'язання. Мереживо*, in: *Етнографічні групи українців Карпат. Гуцули*, ред. С. Павлюка, Харків 2020, с. 232–252.

Among the multidirectional and diversity of Hutsul folk art, special attention was paid to traditional clothes and fabrics – shape, cutting, colors, decorations, lots of jewelry and decorative fabrics (lace making, embroidery, knitting) which were quite unusual for urban culture, especially for foreigners. Deliberate searching for antiques for private and museum collections, gift or purchase of products as travel souvenirs – this is how Hutsul collections were created in Polish museums before 1939. During World War II, most museums continued to operate, mainly under German occupation. During the last years of the war, mainly in connection with the evacuation of the Germans, many exhibits were destroyed, taken away or plundered. This adversely affected the integrity of the museum collections.

However, in the following post-war years, the interest in collecting works of Hutsul art did not cease. But from the mid-twentieth century, as a result of historical and political changes, there were changes in the statutory documents of Polish museums (all became state property), which later to some extent influenced the number of museums, the specificity and future fate of their collections.

At the turn of the XX and XXI centuries, the popularization of the cultural heritage of various ethnographic groups was updated, among which the Hutsul region is quite popular. This is evidenced by a number of temporary thematic exhibitions (based on museum collections or private collections) organized in Polish museum institutions over the last half century. Exhibitions differed in concept – from presenting Hutsul culture as archaic and mythologized to its presentation as one of the Polish national styles; exposition, filling, number of exhibits and finally a response among visitors and professionals. There are also active trips to the Hutsul region of scientists, professors and students (often as part of Polish-Ukrainian cooperation), resulting in a number of scientific and popular science publications on the Hutsul region. Tourists again buy contemporary souvenirs made by Hutsul craftsmen, look for remains of antiquities, record Hutsul types, life and landscapes on „digital” media, admire the colors of Hutsul costumes and textiles, listen to legends about Hutsul life – as well as over a hundred years ago.

A collection of Hutsul costumes and decorative fabrics (lace making, embroidery), today stored at the Ethnographic Museum of Krakow. It was formed in several stages and is related to the history of two museums: the Museum of Technology and Industry (MTP)² (dissolved 1950) and the National Museum in Krakow (NMK), where most of the collections of the Technology and Industry Museum were transferred after its liquidation. From the NMK, they were transferred to the MEK in 1939 as a deposit and in 1989 (date of entry into the MEK Inventory Book). The origin of the artifacts is also evidenced by the metrics on the objects, which to some extent emphasize the historical value of the collections and make it possible to locate them in time. The main part of the collection comes from the end of the XIX and the first half of the XX century (until the outbreak of World War II). The Hutsul collection was shaped thanks to private donors (Seweryn Udziela, Helena Dombchanska, Cecylia S’niegocka, Helena Krasuska and others)³. It is worth noting that even today there are individual cases of transferring Hutsul cultural monuments to the museum⁴.

² S.Till, *Powstanie Muzeum Przemysłowego i Krajowego Instytutu Popierania Rękodziel i przemysłu w Krakowie. Przeszłość, stan obecny, ogólne sprawozdanie za 1911 do 1913, szkic planu na przyszłość*, Kraków 1914, 62 s; *Zapomniane Muzeum, Adrian Baraniecki i Muzeum Techniczno-Przemysłowe 1868–1950. Katalog wystawy czasowej*, Kraków 2013, 92 s; M.Dolińska, *Kolekcja etnograficzna muzeum techniczno-przemysłowego w Krakowie*, in: Мистецька культура: історія, теорія, методологія: тези доповідей VII Міжнар. Наук. конф., НАН України, ЛННБ України ім. В. Стефаника, Ін-т досліджень бібліотечних мистецьких ресурсів; ред.-упоряд. О.Осадця, Л.Купчинська; відп. ред. Л.Сніцарчук Львів 2021, s. 344-351.

³ *Lista osób, które od czasu założenia Muzeum Techniczno-Przemysłowego w Krakowie ofiarami swymi wzbogaciły istniejące zbiory*, Kraków 1869, 8 s.

⁴ *Zapomniane Muzeum. Adrian Baraniecki i Muzeum Techniczno-Przemysłowe 1868–1950. Katalog wystawy czasowej*, Kraków 2013, 92 s.

The necessity to create an ethnographic department (and ultimately a museum) both in Poland in general and directly in Krakow resulted from the active development of ethnographic museums in the world and the interest in the cultural diversity of the peoples living in the region. The formation of an appropriate collection has been partially enshrined in the statutes of the National Museum, incl. the goal of the Museum is to present the state of art and culture in Poland – both in terms of history and at the beginning of the XX century.

It became an important basis for initiating the establishment in 1904 of an ethnographic department at the National Museum (officially opened on January 9, 1904), where the exhibits presented to the general public the importance and uniqueness of folk art, which was already perceived as such, which disappears with everyone. day and requires active behavior.

The aim of the ethnographic collection is to familiarize with folk culture, various fields of art, decorative values of products, as well as to encourage visitors to aesthetics and understand the importance of preserving cultural heritage. Access to the collection helped experts in ethnographic research, and craftsmen and artists – in discovering the best examples of folk art.

The basis of the collection, which was formed quite quickly, consisted of objects from the National Museum, private collections, including the famous ethnographer Seweryn Udziela, as well as the collections of county councils in Buchach, Drohobych, Grybowo, Kamyanka Strumylowa, Nisko and Zhywyec. The Polish Applied Art Society, which as already mentioned, it organized its first exhibition at the National Museum and deposited thematic articles in order to establish an ethnographic department there⁵. Due to the lack of exhibition space, the exhibition was arranged according to local features, namely: Krakow (represented south-western Galicia), Podhale, the Kingdom of Poland, Lithuania and Galician Ruthenia (represented together with Podolia, Ukraine, etc.). Among the 252 exhibited objects from the ethnographic department, the Hutsul region was represented by several products – mainly ceramic and wooden. There is no separate information on Hutsul folk clothing or fabrics, but the catalog contains a valuable collection of Ruthenian costumes in Galicia⁶.

However, long-term plans for the development of the ethnographic department in the museum failed after only a few years. Due to the increase in the number of the main collections of the National Museum in 1907, the ethnographic exhibition was first moved to smaller areas, and then the ethnographic department was completely liquidated. Some of the objects were left on deposit at the National Museum, the rest was placed in other rooms outside the museum by Seweryn Udziela. A few years later, the independent history of the Ethnographic Museum in Krakow began, the main purpose of which is to collect ethnography and promote it properly⁷.

The specificity of the National Museum did not envisage deliberate purchases of folk art. After the Technical and Industrial Museum (was closed in 1950), the National Museum became the main heir of its collections, especially ethnographic ones. However, in the 1980s the question of the compliance of individual collections with the profile of the museum arose again. It was decided to transfer those objects of folk art, which did not stand out for artistic features, to Seweryn Udziela Ethnographic Museum in Krakow.

According to the inventory cards of the National Museum (at the time of its development during my research in Polish museum) the Hutsul collection (clothing, fabrics, jewelry, accessories, chests, icons on glass, Easter eggs, etc.) consists of 95 objects, 43 of which are identified as a separate resource «Collection of fabrics and clothing». The collection does not

Zbiory, “Przemysł i Rzemiosło”, R.IV, №4, Kraków 1924, s. 29.

⁵ *Katalog I. Wystawy Towarzystwa “Polska Sztuka Stosowana”*, Kraków 1902, s. 3-19; S.Udziela, *Muzeum Narodowe w Krakowie. Dział etnograficzny*, Kraków 1905, 6 s.

⁶ *Katalog tymczasowy działu etnograficznego*, Kraków 1904, s. 23-24.

⁷ *Sprawozdanie wydziału Towarzystwa Muzeum etnograficznego w Krakowie za rok 1911*, Kraków 1912, s. 1-2; *Sprawozdanie wydziału Towarzystwa Muzeum etnograficznego w Krakowie za rok 1912*, Kraków 1913, 14 s.; *Sprawozdanie wydziału Towarzystwa Muzeum etnograficznego w Krakowie za rok 1913*, Kraków 1914, 20 s.

Foto: The emblem of the Ethnographic Museum in Krakow in the times of functioning at Wawel (Published: *Sprawozdanie wydziału Towarzystwa Muzeum etnograficznego w Krakowie za rok 1917*, Kraków 1914, 20 s.)

fully present the typological, local and ornamental variety of Hutsul folk fabrics and clothing, but it sufficiently supplements the collection of Hutsul art in Polish museums.

The most valuable „huculiana”, especially in terms of the historical paradigm, is the collection of the Seweryn Udziela, whose creation is associated with the collections of the two previous museums. A significant part of the museum’s collection is the private collection of Seweryn Udziela. It was then supplemented by donors or deliberate purchases, which is recorded in annual reports. This is extremely important information because it allows the dating of objects. Hutsul products were actually labeled „Hutsul”, but it is likely that they could have been labeled „Ruthenian” or as Bukovinian or Pokutia. Moreover, it is not always specified exactly what these items are – information rather generalized. Therefore, the number of products in the museum collection that are directly identified as Hutsul can only be approximated.

The Hutsul collection was constantly replenished thanks to donors and deliberate purchases of products, especially in the interwar period, when the Hutsul region became one of the places eagerly visited by tourists, local historians and artists. In the second half of the XX century, the works of Hutsul folk art were supplemented by the funds of the Ethnographic Museum, mainly in the form of gifts. As I have already mentioned, in the 1980s, after the reform of the Technical and Industrial Museum and the transfer of its collections to the National Museum, and later a significant part of the ethnographic collections to the MEK, the Hutsul collection was also supplemented. Therefore, it can be safely said that today the collection of Hutsul folk art at MEK is the oldest in Polish museums. This is indicated by numerous exhibitions, most of which are exhibited „huculianu” from the Seweryn Udziela Ethnographic Museum in Krakow.

The Hutsul folk costume is characterized by distinct local features, which are most visible in decoration and, to some extent, typological differentiation – taking into account the interaction of the cultures of neighboring nations and ethnographic groups, border and transition zones, socio-cultural, ethnographic and artistic factors of the XIX – early XXI centuries. However,

the combination of centuries-old traditions and innovations in the production and decoration of traditional clothing and textiles in the Hutsul region resulted in a gradual „departure” from the usual and influenced the emergence of new, „different” forms of clothing and fabrics, the development of which was dictated by subsequent times. Given this, we can talk about the variety of Hutsul ornaments, the uniqueness of the patterns is not only generalized, but also quite local. It was the decorativeness of Hutsul clothing and textiles that caused a specific boom in demand for „hutsuliana”, which in turn contributed to the creation of unique private and museum collections.

In Polish museums there are valuable collections of decorative art of the Hutsul region, among which the collections of clothing and textiles deserve special attention. In fact, the variety of shapes, colors, decorations and manufacturing techniques reflects this unique Hutsul color, which has fascinated connoisseurs of traditional highlander culture for over a century. This is evidenced by the large collection of the Hutsul Region at the MEK and the NMK, whose history is related to the history of another Krakow museum – Technical and Industrial.

Items from these three museums „migrated” through the collections, were deposited, so tracing the origin of the product is a kind of search history. In fact, due to the fact that the signatures of the product’s origin are not always reliable, it is very difficult to precisely indicate their final number in Hutsul collections. Sometimes absolutely „non-Hutsul” products are included in the Hutsul region, or Hutsul products are among other ethnographic groups. The issue of borders, or rather borderlands, is controversial.

Particularly interesting are the issues of multiculturalism, the influence of urban fashion and the promotion of female handicrafts, the interaction of tradition and profession, which was to some extent manifested in Hutsul clothing and textiles.

The collections are of historical value – most of the items come from the last quarter of the XIX - the first thirty years of the XX century. Valuable products, especially from an artistic point of view: original ancient ornaments or colors, which at the modern stage are practically unusual for the Hutsul region. For example, the uniqueness of the Hutsul Seweryn Udziela Ethnographic Museum in Krakow collection is evidenced by the active use of objects at various thematic exhibitions in Poland.

Each Hutsul product is a separate story, part of a slightly mythologized, but still mysterious culture of the Carpathian highlanders. The possibility of touching an over a hundred-year-old monument through the prism of a modern worldview opens up new ways of understanding the uninterrupted tradition of the unique Hutsul art.